

Source code, numerical simulations, and post processing scripts described in the research article "Coupling the atmospheric model Meso-NH-v5.5 with the Monte-Carlo solver of conductive-radiative-convective heat exchanges stardis-v0.11.1 to calculate the surface energy balance of complex geometries", submitted to Geoscientific Model Development

1.) Meso-NH code

1.1.) Installation of the Meso-NH version employed in the article

The Meso-NH code (CeCILL-C license) version that has been used for the simulations presented in the article is provided in the MNH-ladev.tar.gz archive that can be extracted using the commands:

```
gunzip MNH-ladev.tar.gz
tar -xvf MNH-ladev.tar
```

The code can be installed on a Linux computer with the commands:

```
cd MNH-ladev/src/
export VER_USER=""
export OPTLEVEL="O2"
./configure
.../conf/profile_mesonh-LXgfortran-R8I4-MNH-V5-5-0-MPIAUTO-O2
make
make installmaster
```

The executables of Meso-NH can be found in

```
./dir_obj-LXgfortran-R8I4-MNH-V5-5-0-MPIAUTO-O2/MASTER/
```

- PREP_IDEAL_CASE: the Meso-NH preprocessor for idealised topography
- MESONH: the Meso-NH programme

Given the high computational cost of the Meso-NH-stardis simulations described in the article, Meso-NH would have to be installed on a supercomputer. In this case, the installation commands would have to be adapted to the specific machine. Information on how to install Meso-NH on different machines can be found in the ./MNH-ladev/A-INSTALL file, in the section "VI) COMPILING/INSTALLING MESONH ON GENCI & ECMWF & METEO & CALMIP COMPUTERS"

1.2) Location of the modified code described in the article

The routine *ibm_stardis_driver.f90* (./MNH-ladev/src/MNH/ibm_stardis_driver.f90) contains the calculation of the meteorological forcing for stardis (Section 2.3, Appendix A), the writing of the forcing (Section 2.3), and the calculation of the sensible heat flux (Section 2.4).

2.) The stardis code including the COSMO library

2.1) Installation of the stardis code

The stardis code (GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE Version 3) version that has been used for the simulations presented in the article is provided in the `GIT_MC2_TREF_KDTREE.tar.gz` archive that can be extracted using the commands:

```
gunzip GIT_MC2_TREF_KDTREE.tar.gz
tar -xvf GIT_MC2_TREF_KDTREE.tar
```

This code can be installed on a Linux computer by executing the list of commands in the file `./GIT_MC2_TREF_KDTREE/Install.txt`

The commands provided in `Install.txt` make sure to install the code versions that are compatible with the model developments described in the article:

- `star-build` installs `stardis` version 0.11.1.
- A commit compatible with the developments in `stardis-documentation` is checked out for `stardis-solver` and `stardis`.
- A tarball is provided for the `stardis-documentation` library, which contains the modifications specific to the simulations for the COSMO site

Stardis can be sourced via the command:

```
source ./GIT_MC2_TREF_KDTREE/stardis-develop/etc/profile
```

2.2) Location of the modified code described in the present article

The library that has been developed for the coupling of stardis with Meso-NH (Section 2.2, Section 3.3.2) is located in

```
./GIT_MC2_TREF_KDTREE/stardis-documentation/StarterPack/src/
```

The main program is `cosmo_prog.c`, which contains the routines:

- `stardis_create_library_data`: read the image point positions and meteorological forcing data from disc.
- `stardis_convection_coefficient`, `stardis_medium_temperature`, and `stardis_surface_temperature` attribute the value of the exchange coefficient for sensible heat, air temperature, and surface temperature that are required when a conductive-radiative-convective path reaches the solid-atmosphere interface. The closest point in the forcing data is taken. A linear interpolation in time is performed.
- `stardis_spherical_source_position` reads the position of the sun.
- `stardis_spherical_source_power` calculates the power of the sun coherent with the direct solar radiation simulated by Meso-NH.
- `stardis_spherical_source_diffuse_radiance` calculates the power of the sun coherent with the diffuse solar radiation simulated by Meso-NH.
- `stardis_radiative_env_temperature` calculates the effective sky temperature as a function of the downwelling terrestrial infrared radiation simulated by Meso-NH.

3.) The Meso-NH-stardis related namelists and configuration files

Conductive-radiative-convective heat exchanges in a 3-D urban geometry is configured via new entries in the NAM_IBM_PARAMn namelist in the EXSEG1.nam Meso-NH configuration file.

Table 1: The new entries in the NAM_IBM_PARAMn namelist specific to the newly introduced conductive-radiative-convective heat exchanges.

Variable	Type	Default	Meaning
LIBM_HEAT	Logical	.FALSE.	Activation of conductive-radiative-convective heat exchanges between immersed obstacles.
CCH_IBM	Character (*5)	DOE-2	The option for the calculation of the exchange coefficient for sensible heat <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOE-2: Exchange coefficient following the DOE-2 model described in Appendix A (recommended) • ROW30: Exchange coefficient following Rowley et al. (1930). • MOBUK: Exchange coefficient following Monin-Obukhov similarity theory.
XIBM_HEAT_WT	Real	Δt_{MNH}	Time step for writing the meteorological forcing (Δt_{FRC})
XIBM_HEAT_DT	Real	Δt_{MNH}	Time step for calculating the conductive-radiative-convective heat exchanges (Δt_{STA})
CZ0H_IBM	Character (*6)	KAND07	Option for the calculation of the exchange coefficients following Monin-Obukhov theory. Only used for CCH_IBM=MOBUK. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BRUT82: Brutsaert (1982) • KAND07: Kanda et al. (2007) • MASC95: Mascart et al. (1995)
XZ0_O_Z0H_IBM	Real	1.0	Ratio between the aerodynamical and thermal roughness length. Only used for CCH_IBM=MOBUK.

The other namelist entries related to the existing Meso-NH code are explained in the Meso-NH technical documentation (http://mesonh.aero.obs-mip.fr/mesonh55/BooksAndGuides?action=AttachFile&do=get&target=users_guide_m551.pdf).

4.) The run directories corresponding to the Meso-NH-stardis simulations presented in the article

The run directories are provided in the RUNDIRS.tar.gz folder that can be unpacked with *gunzip RUNDIRS.tar.gz*
tar -xvf RUNDIRS.tar

4.1) Meso-NH preprocessor

The Meso-NH preprocessor (PREP_IDEAL_CASE) needs to be executed once for the 0.15 m resolution grid (configurations 10P, DL2, DL8, 4REA, STD60; 001_prep_ideal_case_10PPL folder) and once for the 0.075 m resolution grid (configuration 20P; 001_prep_ideal_case_20PPL folder).

The meteorological forcing data for the August 19 2014 to August 22 2014 period obtained from the observations at the COSMO site are prescribed as vertical profile each 1800 s at the end of the Meso-NH preprocessor namelist (PRE_IDEA1.nam).

4.2) Meso-NH-stardis simulations

The model configurations described in the article are the following:

- COSMO_DOE-2_10PPL_DELTA2MM corresponds to the DL2 configuration.
- COSMO_DOE-2_10PPL_DELTA8MM corresponds to the DL8 configuration.
- COSMO_DOE-2_10PPL_DREA corresponds to the 4REA configuration.
- COSMO_DOE-2_10PPL_MTO300 corresponds to the MTO300 configuration.
- COSMO_DOE-2_10PPL_REFERER corresponds to the REF configuration.
- COSMO_DOE-2_10PPL_STD60 corresponds to the STD60 configuration.
- COSMO_DOE-2_20PPL corresponds to the 20P configuration.

The simulations are supposed to be launched on a supercomputer using a series of *slurm* jobs. The first *slurm* job to be launched by the user is *job_slurm_MAIN_INI*. The user can specify the values of Δt_{FRC} (wrtlen) and Δt_{STA} (seglen) and the re-injection length (δ). The *slurm* script then launches a python programme (MAIN.py) which controls the execution of Meso-NH and stardis for one segment consisting of a Meso-NH simulation with the duration of *seglen* and a call of stardis at the end of the segment. The value of the time step used in Meso-NH (Δt_{MNH}) is specified in MAIN_TEMPLATE.py as a function of the time of day (*xtstep*). The number of realisations of the Monte-Carlo algorithm (*N*) is also specified in MAIN_TEMPLATE.py as a function of the time of day (*nreal*).

The initial values of the temperatures of the cube top (*ROOF*), cube walls (*WALL*), ground (*ROAD*), and indoor air (*TIBLD*) are prescribed in *vars_PP_template.sh*. *vars_PP_template.sh* contains also the material parameters for the different solids, which are heat conductivity (W/m/K) (*LAMBDA*), density (kg/m³) (*RHO*), specific heat capacity (J/kg) (*CP*), whereas the values for albedo (0.14), solar specular reflection fraction (0.0), and terrestrial infrared emissivity (0.89) are specified in *model_prog_header_template.txt*.

It is admitted that the current way to run the simulations is not efficient because

- The *job_slurm_MAIN* runs idle while waiting for Meso-NH or stardis to finish.
- Costly Meso-NH restarts are made each time the conductive-radiative-convective exchanges with stardis are calculated.

No effort has been made to improve the efficiency since potential future scientific and technical developments (symbolic Monte-Carlo or the use of a dedicated coupler) will improve the coupling. However, these potential improvements will be validated against the results of the robust coupling method introduced in the present work.

5.) Post processing

The post processing scripts are given in *Postprocessing.tar.gz* that can be extracted via *gunzip Postprocessing.tar.gz*
tar -xvf Postprocessing.tar

For the post processing, first the district average sensible heat flux and the profile of air temperature at the location of the thermocouples are extracted from the Meso-NH output files. This is made using the scripts *Extract_Profile.py* and *Extract_SENFLUX.py*. The full 3D Meso-NH outputs are not provided due to the large file size. They are however archived on the *hendrix* archive at Météo-France.

The results of the *Extract_Profile.py* and *Extract_SENFLUX.py* scripts are provided in *Data.tar.gz* that can be unpacked with the commands
gunzip Data.tar.gz
tar -xvf Data.tar

The *EVAL_TS_COSMO.R* script creates the time series figures (Figure 6, 7, and 8). The observational data from the COSMO site are included since version 2 of this dataset and are located in the *COSMO_Data.tar.gz* folder.

The *EVAL_TEMPERATURE_COSMO.R* script creates the vertical profiles figures (Figure 9, 10, and 11). The observational data from the COSMO site are included since version 2 of this dataset and are located in the *COSMO_Data.tar.gz* folder.

The *Evaluation_against_camera.py* script performs the validation of skin surface temperature with the thermal camera results (Figures 12 and 13). The thermal camera observations are included since version 3 of this dataset and are located in the *COSMO_Camera.tar.gz* folder.

The *ANALYSIS_TS_COSMO_CAMERA.R* script creates Figure 14 on the sensitivity of the camera observations to surface and sky emissivity.

The *EVAL_CONVERGENCE_TS_COSMO.R* script creates Figure 15 on the convergence of the Monte-Carlo algorithm.

References

- Brutsaert, W., 1982. *Evaporation into the Atmosphere: Theory, History and Applications*, Reidel, Dordrecht, 299 pp.
- Kanda, M., M. Kanega, T. Kawai, R. Moriwaki, and H. Sugawara, 2007: Roughness Lengths for Momentum and Heat Derived from Outdoor Urban Scale Models. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 46, 1067–1079, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAM2500.1>.
- Mascart, P., J. Noilhan, and H. Giordani, 1995: A modified parameterization of flux-profile relationships in the surface layer using different roughness length values for heat and momentum. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 72, 331–344, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00708998>.
- Rowley, F.B., A.B. Algren, and J. Blackshaw, 1930: Effects of air velocity on surface coefficients. *ASHRAE*, 36, 123.